

**3rd International
Radiocarbon
in the Environment
Conference**

5-9 July 2021, Gliwice, Poland

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Comparative dating of charcoal, tooth and ceramic samples from the Polutepe archaeological site in Azerbaijan

Aybaniz Ahadova, Sahib Mammadov

Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences, Institute of Radiation Problems

The radiocarbon dating method was used to date the age of a charcoal sample from the Polutepe archaeological site in the Jalilabad district of Azerbaijan. Polutepe is the largest Neolithic-Eneolithic monument in the Caucasus. A charcoal sample excavated at the Polutepe site was dated by the conventional radiocarbon method at 4270 ± 160 BC, which agrees with the stratigraphic estimated dates. ESR method has also been applied to determine the age of tooth enamel found in Polutepe archaeological site. The investigated object was presumable the lower jaw of a cow with well-preserved tooth. The mean age of the sample was determined as 5420 ± 130 BC years. The age of fragments of the ancient pottery sample from the same archaeological site has been estimated by employing Thermoluminescence dating method. The age of the sample was calculated by an additive dose method as 4360 ± 530 BC years which are in line with the charcoal samples.

Conference Programme

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Division of Geochronology and Environmental Isotopes

Institute of Physics – Centre for Science and Education

Silesian University of Technology

Konarskiego 22B, 44-100 Gliwice, Poland

What do we do?

Division of Geochronology and Environmental Isotopes is a unique scientific unit, where nineteen persons delve into the fundamentals of physical isotope methods and their applications. We are engaged in interdisciplinary research projects in Earth and environmental sciences, archaeology and history. We also offer expertise services for national and foreign institutions.

Two Laboratories are functioning within the Division:

1. Radiocarbon and Mass Spectrometry Laboratory

- Radiocarbon measurements with various techniques (LSC, AMS)
- Light stable isotope determinations (HCNO) with IRMS

2. Luminescence Dating Laboratory

- Dosimetric dating methods (OSL, TL)
- Radioisotope measurements (γ and α spectrometry, e.g. ^{137}Cs , ^{210}Pb)

Why do we do it?

The isotope methods find its applications to construct the calendar timescales for Earth and human history, for geology, geomorphology, palaeoclimatic research, palaeogeography. They also allow to trace natural environmental processes and human impact. Isotopes have proved to be invaluable tools for biological research, like palaeobotany or dendrology, for anthropology, archaeology and palaeozoology - e.g. for diet reconstructions.

What do we offer?

- Work with a team of specialist in various isotope methods
- Gain experience in multidisciplinary research
- Get involved in international cooperation

Contact person Head of the Division of Geochronology and Environmental Isotopes
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Monday 05 July 2021: **Methods**

9:30-10:10

Andrzej Rakowski

Opening

chair: Andrzej Rakowski

Session 1

10:10-10:50

Walter Kutschera (invited speaker)

The versatile uses of the ^{14}C bomb peak

10:50-11:30

Hans-Arno Synal (invited speaker)

Progress in AMS and Opportunities for Applications in
Environment Research

11:30-11:50

coffee break

Session 2

chair: Irka Hajdas

11:50-12:10

Hangtao Shen

The ^{14}C -AMS technology and it's applications for evaluation
of the Properties of highly permeable aquifers cause by large
volume water injection in oil field

12:10-12:30

Gianluca Quarta

The IAEA forensics program: results of the AMS ^{14}C inter-
comparison exercise on contemporary wines and coffees

12:30-12:50

Konstantin Pustovoytov

^{14}C in biogenic carbonate of plant origin: environmental
factors and potential for radiocarbon dating

12:50-13:10

Aybaniz Ahadova

Comparative Dating of Charcoal, Tooth and Ceramic Samples
from the Polutepe Archeological Site in Azerbaijan

13:10-14:10

lunch break